

ROLE OF AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT IN RAKTPRADAR (MENORRHAGIA)- A SINGLE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Raktpradar is one of the most common gynecological problem seen nowadays due to altered lifestyle, dietary changes and hormonal imbalance because of stressful living. It is associated with excessive menstrual bleeding. According to *charak acharya*, *Raktpradar* means '*pradirana* (excessive excretion) of *Raja* (menstrual bleeding) Resulting from Imbalance of *Rakta* and *pitta dosha*. Ayurveda approaches a comprehensive treatment plan that includes herbal medicines Panchakarma therapy, dietary changes, and lifestyle modifications aimed at restoring menstrual health. The objective of this study is to assess the effectiveness of *Ayurvedic* treatment in addressing *Raktapradara* through a detailed case analysis, focusing on the role of *ayurvedic* interventions and Panchakarma therapy in normalizing and regularize menstrual cycles and enhancing overall health. In the methods section, a 32-year-old woman experiencing heavy menstrual bleeding for the duration of more than 9 days received *Ayurvedic* treatment. In the present study, it is observed that *Pathya-Apathya* with medication has a significant role in relieving symptoms of *Raktapradar*.

KEYWORDS: *Raktapradar*, *Pathya-Apathya*.

INTRODUCTION

As per incidence 30-40% of women of reproductive age suffer excessive or irregular menstrual bleeding due to various factors. Heavy menstrual bleeding is managed by modern hormonal or medical and surgical treatment, This treatment has a lot of side effects and if it fails then surgical intervention is indicated. Because of the limitation of medical and surgical therapy in Allopathy, it becomes a need to find out alternative effective and harmless therapy to manage excessive or irregular uterine bleeding. In Ayurveda length of the normal cycle (28-30 days) and the duration of bleeding time (4-5 days) are mentioned. Normally in a healthy girl, menarche occurs 11-15 years with a time interval of 28-30 days, and the duration of bleeding is about 4-5 days. In *Raktapradar* there is an increased amount and duration of blood flow during menses. In Ayurvedic text, the causative factor of *Raktapradar* has been mentioned. The management and prevention of *Raktapradar* are also mentioned. Many preparations have been mentioned in our Samhitas for *RaktaPradar*. All these preparation have a certain common basic principle of Ayurveda. So keeping in mind all of the above reasons, the present study has been selected.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

1. To evaluate the effectiveness of ayurvedic treatment in managing *raktpradar*.
2. To assess the role of herbal and panchakarma interventions in restoring menstrual health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A single case study

A 32 yr/F with excessive and prolonged menstrual bleeding.

Intervention-ayurvedic treatment including oral medications and panchkarma treatment with dietary advice.

Duration -3 month

CASE PRESENTATION

A 32 yr/F came to streeroga and prasutitantra department with c/o excessive and prolonged bleeding during menstruation. her cycle is regular with 7-8 days duration of menstrual bleeding with soakage of 5-6 pads/day, associated with general weakness. she had no any past history or systemic diseases. no any surgical history .no any drug history noted.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

PR -82/min

BP-110/80 mmhg P/A- soft, NT Pallor- present

INVESTIGATIONS

Hb- 9gm/dl

USG (abdomen and pelvis)-NAD

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

Oral medications-

Sr. No	Drugs	Dose	Duration
1	Shunthi-lodhra churn	5gm bd with ghrut (7 days From 5 th day of menses)	3 months
2	Raktapachak kashay	15 ml with water From 5 th day of menses)	3 months
3	Bolbadhh ras	2bd with water From 5 th day of menses	3 months
4	Ashokarishta	20 ml bd with equal water	3 months
5	Navayas louh vati	2 bd with water	3 months

Dietary and Lifestyle Modifications

Advised- Fresh cooked meal, milk, fresh fruits, cow ghee.

Daily yoga and meditation.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

- After three months of treatment.
- the patient showed significant improvement.
- Menstrual flow reduced to 4 days with moderately bleeding.
- General health improved. pallor has reduced.
- 3 mnths treatment tolerated well by patient.

DISCUSSION

The ayurvedic management approach includes *pitta* pacifying herbs, *raktastambhak* medicines, uterine tonics all aimed at regulating the menstrual cycle. Ashokarishta has significant use in *raktapradar*. it has hemostatic and uterine tonic properties. Raktapachak kshay used to purify rakt dhatu. bolbaddha ras it has hemostatic and astringent properties, it has guduchi stva which pasify *pitta dosh* and beneficial in *raktapradar* also *bola or Myrrh* is a gum resin which act as *stambhak*. shunthi and lodhra churn act as *dipan, pachak and stambhak* properties. to restore haemoglobin used navayas lauh vati. In addition to this dietary and lifestyle changes play a crucial role in management of *raktpradar*.

CONCLUSION

This study signifies the efficacy of ayurvedic treatment in *raktpradar* by using herbal medicines, dietary modifications and lifestyle changes. Integrating cooling and nutrient containing food. The patient reported improved regularities of menstrual cycle. Overall general health and improved physical and mental health.

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